

PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF THE TRANSLATOR

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Annotation: *In the process of creating professional translation competence, a peculiar language personality is formed, which has a number of differences from the “normal”, non-translation personality. These differences are revealed in all the main aspects of speech communication: language, text-forming, communicative, personal and professional-technical.*

Key words: *The organization of training, special methodological techniques, linguistic, professional translator.*

The organization of training translators is largely determined by the fact that the translator has to perform very diverse types of activities that provide different forms of language communication. Teaching different types of translation requires special methodological techniques. A professional translator can specialize in one or more types of translation.

The diversity of translation activities is associated not only with different types of translation. Translation can be performed under different conditions, within a more or less strict time frame, with a variety of goals, and for different customers. The translation text may be intended for general acquaintance with the original, for obtaining some information, or for publication as a full-fledged replacement of the original. In all these cases, different requirements are imposed on translation, and the translator must be prepared to work in a wide variety of conditions.

The nature of a translator’s work is also influenced by their official status. They can work on the staff of a bureau or department, alone or as part of a group of

translators, can act as a “freelance artist”, performing translations under contracts and contracts, can act as a translation editor or head of a “team” of translators, etc.

Finally, the translator can be assigned many types of "near translation" activities: conducting negotiations, business correspondence, receiving and accompanying delegations, drawing up reviews, minutes of conversations and other documentation, language and country-specific consultations, etc.

The specifics of cross-language communication and various forms of translation activity make it necessary to create a translator's own translation competence, which is characterized by some distinctive features.

The language competence of an interpreter includes all aspects of language proficiency that are characteristic of any native speaker, but also implies a number of specific features. Just like any participant in language communication, the translator stores in his memory knowledge about the system, norm and usage of the language, its vocabulary and grammatical structure, the rules for using language units for constructing speech utterances, the predominant use of certain sets of language units in various areas of communication, territorial, social and professional differences in the use of such units, the impact on the choice and nature of the use of language units of the communication environment and relationships of communication participants, their role functions.

At the same time, the specific nature of the translator's speech activity imposes additional requirements on his / her language competence, which are due not only to the fact that the translator must have sufficient language competence in the field of not one, but two languages. First of all, it should be noted that unlike "normal" native speakers, the nature and boundaries of the translator's language competence are largely imposed from the outside. An ordinary communicant has a certain level of language proficiency, which he uses at his own discretion, independently choosing the means of expression from his idiolect, according to the purpose and situation of communication, in determining which he takes a direct part. At the same time, it can manage with a limited set of language tools, without

participating in acts of communication that require more extensive or more effective use of a language that exceeds its capabilities. For the translator, the scope and purpose of communication, the choice and method of using language means are largely set by the original and do not depend on his own desire. Therefore, the translator must have a comprehensive language competence in both receptive and productive terms, in both languages involved in the translation process. Of course, each translator's language competence has its own limits, but the wider these limits, the higher their overall professional competence.

The potentially unlimited requirements for the translator's language competence imply the need to be able to quickly expand and supplement their language knowledge, especially in comparative terms. A translator is a person in constant search, constantly asking himself how to say it in another language, what does this word mean, and what is said in this language in this situation? This is a person who, by listening and reading, hears and sees not only what is said, but also how it is said, who does not part with dictionaries, does not miss an opportunity to learn something new about the language, to replenish his file cabinet.

Successful exchange of speech works in the process of communication implies that communicants have a text-forming competence, the ability to create texts of different types in accordance with the rules and stereotypes adopted in this language team. The professional competence of a translator includes knowledge of the correlation of such rules in two languages and the ability to construct texts of different types.